

On the Preparation of Dithiophosphates and some new Dithiophosphates.

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Sodium monothiophosphate was first obtained by Wurtz (*Ann. chim. phys.*, 1847, iii 20, 443) by the interaction of caustic soda and phosphorus thiochloride. Kubierschky (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1885, ii, 31, 93) obtained several mono- and di-thiophosphates by the action of caustic soda on phosphorous pentasulphide. The solution thus obtained probably contained trithiophosphate as well, but it was not isolated. He, however, separated the three varieties of thiophosphates by variation in temperatures. We repeated his experiments but found it extremely difficult to obtain the thiophosphates in the pure condition. The mixture formed by the action of caustic soda on phosphorous pentasulphide was treated by Kubierschky with alcohol and the resultant oil was separated, dissolved in water and heated to 50°-55° to decompose the trithiophosphate and to 90° to decompose the dithiophosphate as well, leaving the monothiophosphate undecomposed. But our experience showed that heating the solution to a particular temperature failed to separate the three thiophosphates except with great difficulty. Kubierschky advised to heat the solution until the smell of sulphuretted hydrogen was no longer perceived. On heating the solution however, we found it to be blackened, and sulphuretted hydrogen was evolved continuously even when heated for two or three days at the particular temperatures mentioned by him. The resultant crystals from such solutions were impure and were separated with great difficulty. There are no methods for preparing the several varieties of thiophosphates singly without the accompaniment of other varieties.

The method, which succeeded so far as dithiophosphates are concerned, was the interaction of powdered phosphorous pentasulphide on magnesium oxide suspended in ice-cold water (*vide* Experimental), the reaction being as follows :

The sodium salt was obtained by double decomposition with caustic soda. In the case of other soluble thiophosphates such

as those of potassium, ammonium and calcium the corresponding hydroxides were used in the place of caustic soda. Insoluble dithiophosphates were prepared by double decomposition of the sodium salt with soluble salts of different metals. By this method we have been able to prepare dithiophosphates of sodium potassium, calcium, ammonium, barium, magnesium, lead, thallium and zinc. The potassium, calcium, magnesium, lead, thallium and zinc compounds were hitherto unknown. Other dithiophosphates such as those of manganese, mercury (ic), thorium and lanthanum were also obtained, but they decomposed during drying. What were presumably dithiophosphates of bismuth, copper, mercury (ous), nickel, cobalt, cadmium, silver and ferrous iron were found to be still more unstable and decomposed within a few seconds of their precipitation. Their decomposition could be avoided for a few more seconds by the immediate addition of excess of alcohol, but even in the presence of alcohol their decomposition could not be prevented. It is to be understood that all operations including precipitations and filtrations were done in vessels containing ice and salt, washing being done with ice-water.

As regards the other varieties of thiophosphates, Kubierschky obtained the three varieties in the oil obtained by precipitation with alcohol. The oil or crystals obtained by our method did not contain either the mono- or tri-thiophosphates, so that this is a method of preparing dithiophosphates only.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Sodium Dithiophosphate, $\text{Na}_3\text{PS}_2\text{O}_2 + 11\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Magnesia (80 g.) was suspended in water in a beaker surrounded with ice and salt, and finely powdered phosphorous pentasulphide (22 g.) was then added. The brisk action which followed was allowed to proceed for 2-3 hours in order to complete the reaction, the beaker being kept surrounded with ice all the while. The solution was then filtered off from the excess of the reagents in a metallic funnel containing ice-water and a clear yellowish solution was obtained. From this solution the magnesium was precipitated as the hydroxide by adding a cold solution of caustic soda in small quantities at a time, avoiding excess. The completion of the decomposition was ascertained by filtering off a small portion from time to time until with the addition of only a few drops of the caustic soda solution no further precipitate of magnesium hydroxide was noticed.

The whole of the magnesium hydroxide was now filtered off and to the clear filtrate an excess of cold alcohol was added. Very soon beautiful six-sided crystals were deposited and when the deposition was complete, the alcohol was decanted off and the crystals washed several times with alcohol in order to remove the impurities such as any adhering caustic soda and alkali sulphides. These were further purified by redissolving the crystals in water and reprecipitating with excess of alcohol. The crystals being washed with alcohol, rapidly became dry when pressed between filter papers. The salt responded to all the tests of dithiophosphates as given by Kubierschky of which the following are important and not given by other thiophosphates. A solution of sodium salt was used in all these tests.

(1) On the gradual addition of manganous sulphate solution, at first a green colouration was observed which on shaking turned darker and on further addition of the sulphate, gave a green precipitate which gradually became white. But this white precipitate on shaking changed its colour again and turned green.

(2) A solution of cobalt sulphate gave a green precipitate soluble in excess of sodium dithiophosphate to a green solution which rapidly became black owing to the formation of cobalt sulphide.

The dry salt was analysed and found to have the formula $\text{Na}_3\text{PS}_2\text{O}_2 + 11\text{H}_2\text{O}$, which agreed with Kubierschky's formula of the salt. The sulphur was oxidised to sulphate with concentrated nitric acid and bromine water and estimated as barium sulphate. The phosphate was estimated by dissolving the salt in concentrated hydrochloric acid, precipitating with magnesia mixture and estimating as pyrophosphate. (Found: S, 15.91; P, 8.63. $\text{Na}_3\text{PS}_2\text{O}_2, 11\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires S, 16.24; P, 7.86 per cent.). The sodium and other hydrated salts give out water when heated.

Potassium Dithiophosphate, $\text{K}_3\text{PS}_2\text{O}_2 + 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Potassium dithiophosphate was obtained by Kubierschky in solution only. This compound, however, was obtained by us as a crystalline solid by the following method.

Phosphorus pentasulphide (15 g.) was allowed to react with magnesium oxide (21 g.) as previously described. The solution was filtered and caustic potash solution carefully added until the whole of magnesium was just precipitated as magnesium hydroxide. To the solution of the potassium salt thus obtained, an excess of alcohol

was added when an oil separated out. The alcohol was then decanted off and the oil washed several times with alcohol and collected. When kept in a vacuum desiccator over concentrated sulphuric acid inside an ice-chest containing a mixture of ice and salt, it formed a crystalline mass after three or four days. The crystals were rapidly dried between filter papers and analysed. When the oil was kept in a vacuum desiccator over sulphuric acid at the ordinary temperature, it underwent partial decomposition evolving sulphuretted hydrogen. The resulting solid contained very little dithiophosphate. It was not possible to separate the dithiophosphate from this mixture as an oil was again formed on treatment with alcohol. The pure dry salt could be kept undecomposed in an ordinary desiccator in an ice-chest only but slowly decomposed at the ordinary temperature. (Found: S, 20·55; P, 8·91. $K_3PS_2O_2 + 4H_2O$ requires S, 20·25; P, 9·81 per cent.).*

Ammonium Dithiophosphate, $(NH_4)_3PS_2O_2 + 2H_2O$.

The ammonium salt had been obtained by Kubierschky. It was obtained by our method also, substituting caustic soda by ammonium hydroxide. (Found: S, 30·06. $(NH_4)_3PS_2O_2 + 2H_2O$ requires S, 29·49 per cent.).

Magnesium Dithiophosphate, $Mg_3P_2S_4O_4 + \cdot H_2O$.

Magnesium dithiophosphate was obtained by Kubierschky who reported it to be soluble and unstable. No analysis was given and its formula was not established. The magnesium compound as prepared by us was a solid.

Powdered phosphorus pentasulphide (17 g.) was allowed to react with magnesium oxide (23 g.) in the usual manner. When the reaction subsided, the mixture was filtered off and to the filtrate an excess of alcohol was added when the magnesium salt was precipitated. It was washed with alcohol, redissolved in water and reprecipitated with alcohol. The salt was found to be very unstable so much so, that it could not be dried under an electric fan at the ordinary temperature. The salt was dried by keeping overnight in a vacuum desiccator in an ice-chest. It was found to have become

* The error in P is high owing to the small percentage of P. only. Better analytical results are hardly to be expected with such unstable compounds.

partly insoluble in water. (Found: S, 35.56. $Mg_3P_2S_4O_4 + 2H_2O$ requires S, 35.35 per cent.). Owing to the fact that it becomes partly insoluble on reprecipitation, the formula assigned to it here is doubtful.

Calcium Dithiophosphate, $Ca_3P_2S_4O_4 + H_2O$.

The calcium was reported by Kubierschky to be soluble in water and unstable. He could not obtain it pure.

Powdered phosphorus pentasulphide (21 g.) was allowed to act upon magnesia (24 g.) in the usual way. To this solution cold lime water was carefully added avoiding any excess when magnesium hydroxide was precipitated, and the calcium dithiophosphate remaining in solution. The solution was filtered and the calcium salt precipitated with alcohol and purified as in previous cases. The salt being very unstable was dried in the same manner as the magnesium salt. For analysis, a weighed quantity of the salt was dissolved in concentrated nitric acid and the precipitation being completed in excess of absolute alcohol, the sulphate precipitated as $CaSO_4$. This was washed with 70% alcohol. The salt was found to be insoluble in alcohol. (Found: S, 32.03. $Ca_3P_2S_4O_4 + H_2O$ requires S, 32.65 per cent.).

Barium Dithiophosphate, $Ba_3P_2S_4O_4 + 10H_2O$.

To a solution of the sodium salt, barium chloride solution was added when barium dithiophosphate was precipitated. The barium salt was washed with alcohol and dried between filter papers and then under an electric fan. The salt was comparatively stable and insoluble in water and alcohol.

The analysis was done as indicated before; in this case however, part of the sulphur was precipitated out as barium sulphate during oxidation of the salt with concentrated nitric acid and bromine water. The excess of the sulphuric acid was then precipitated by the addition of barium chloride solution. The combined precipitate of barium sulphate was then washed, dried and weighed as usual. (Found: S, 14.81. $Ba_3P_2S_4O_4 + 10H_2O$ requires S, 15.14 per cent.).

Zinc Dithiophosphate, $Zn_3P_2S_4O_4 + H_2O$.

To a solution of the sodium salt, zinc acetate* solution was added when the zinc thiophosphate was obtained as a white precipitate.

* Zinc sulphate solution, being acidic, was not suitable for precipitation, as in the acid solution the thiophosphate underwent decomposition.

It was washed with alcohol, and dried in a vacuum desiccator kept in an ice-chest containing ice and salt. It was a white powder, insoluble both in water and alcohol. (Found: S, 27.29. $\text{Zn}_3\text{P}_2\text{S}_4\text{O}_4 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires S, 27.41 per cent.).

Thallium Dithiophosphate, $\text{Tl}_3\text{P}_2\text{S}_4\text{O}_4$.

A solution of thallos carbonate was added to a solution of the sodium salt, when thallos dithiophosphate was obtained as a yellow precipitate. It was washed with water and finally with alcohol and dried in a vacuum desiccator. The salt is comparatively stable and insoluble in water and alcohol. For estimating thallium a weighed quantity was dissolved in concentrated hydrochloric acid and the solution made almost neutral with the addition of ammonium carbonate. From this solution thallium was estimated as thallos iodide in the usual way. (Found: S, 8.29; Tl, 81.46. $\text{Tl}_3\text{P}_2\text{S}_4\text{O}_4$ requires S, 8.66; Tl, 82.81 per cent.).

Lead Dithiophosphate, $\text{Pb}_3\text{P}_2\text{S}_4\text{O}_4 + 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

The lead compound was obtained as a yellow precipitate by the double decomposition of a solution of sodium dithiophosphate with lead nitrate solution. It was washed with water and finally with alcohol and dried under an electric fan. The lead was estimated by dissolving a weighed quantity of the salt in moderately concentrated hydrochloric acid, and precipitating as sulphide. The sulphide was then converted into the sulphate and estimated as such in the usual way. The sulphur content of the salt was determined in the usual way as barium sulphate after the removal of the lead. (Found: Pb, 35.07; S, 13.77. $\text{Pb}_3\text{P}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Pb, 65.58; S, 13.52 per cent.).

Unstable Dithiophosphates.

The following dithiophosphates could be obtained as solid precipitates but decomposed either during washing or during drying even in a vacuum desiccator over concentrated sulphuric acid in an ice-chest. All of them were, of course, dithiophosphates and contained both sulphur and phosphorus. The manganous and mercuric salts were also noticed by Kubierschky (*loc. cit.*).

Manganous Dithiophosphate.—The manganous salt was precipitated on the addition of a large excess of manganous sulphate solution to a solution of the sodium salt in the cold. With the addition of small

quantities of manganous sulphate solution at first a green solution, as reported by Kubierschky, was obtained which changed to a white precipitate. The white precipitate was washed with ice water and with cold alcohol. It did not decompose during washing but it was impossible to dry it either under the electric fan or in a vacuum desiccator without decomposition.

Mercuric Dithiophosphate.—The mercuric salt was obtained as a yellow precipitate on the addition of a solution of mercuric chloride to a solution of the sodium salt. It was more unstable than the manganous salt and began to decompose during washing.

Thorium Dithiophosphate.—This compound was obtained as a white precipitate by the double decomposition of a solution of thorium nitrate and a solution of sodium dithiophosphate. The precipitate, however, decomposed during washing with ice water.

Lanthanum Dithiophosphate.—This was obtained as a white precipitate by the double decomposition of a solution of lanthanum nitrate and a solution of sodium dithiophosphate. It too decomposed during washing with ice-water.

We would now conclude by briefly referring to other dithiophosphates, which were obtained as precipitates by double decomposition with the sodium salt but decomposed after a few seconds even when precipitated at 0°. With a solution of sodium dithiophosphate coloured precipitates, which were also noticed by Kubierschky, were obtained with bismuth (yellow), mercury (*ous*) (yellow), copper (green), silver (yellow), cobalt (green), nickel (dirty blue) and cadmium (white) salts. These too were extremely unstable and decomposed within a few seconds of their precipitation. A ferrous compound, not noticed by Kubierschky, was obtained as a yellow precipitate by the addition of a solution of Mohr's salt to a solution of sodium dithiophosphate. The compound was found to be extremely unstable and the final product was the sulphide. Attempts were also made to get the dithiophosphates of aluminium, zirconium and molybdenum by the double decomposition of sodium dithiophosphate and the soluble salts of these metals but the results were negative, only sulphuretted hydrogen being evolved.

